

Climatic Variability and Groundnut Crop Yield: Unveiling the Scenario in Anantapur, India

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ABSTRACT

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) cultivation in India relies solely on rainfed conditions and prevailing climatic conditions. The faster rate of change in climate variables combined with the occurrences of extreme weather events have a significant impact on agriculture. In this study, the trend in yield of groundnut at Anantapur, India is computed with respect to the variation in climatic parameters over 2000 to 2019. Indices namely the Soil Moisture Index (SMI), Moisture Availability Index (MAI), Aridity Index (AI), and Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI) were utilized to elucidate the relationship between yield variations and climate variability. The findings reveal a slight hike in groundnut yield, with an increase of 1.1 kg/ha annually, corresponding to augmented wetness (manifested through rainfall and MAI) and diminished dryness (reflected by AI and consecutive dry days for 2D, 3D, & 4D). Notably, wetness indices such as SMI and MAI exhibited strong positive correlations (0.604** and 0.56*, respectively) with yield, while AI displayed a negative correlation (0.557*). Furthermore, NDMI peaks escalated from 0.76 to 0.81, indicating progressive soil moisture levels. These results suggest that climatic fluctuations in Anantapur have positively impacted groundnut yield (77.9% of the variability is explained by the selected predictors) with a discernible prevalence of wet conditions throughout the study period. This study employs both statistical and geospatial component (GEE – Java scripting) to analyse the relationship between groundnut yield and climatic variables, providing insights into the dynamics of agricultural productivity in the Anantapur region.

Keywords: Aridity Index (AI); Moisture Availability Index (MAI); Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI); Soil Moisture Index (SMI).

1. INTRODUCTION

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) stands among the top five crucial oilseed crops globally, holding significant importance for its nutritional content and economic value. It provides a major source of edible oil, protein, and income for millions of smallholder farmers, particularly in tropical and

subtropical regions (Virmani and Shurapli, 1999). The productivity of groundnut varies worldwide due to diverse farming conditions, including differences in agro-climatic zones, soil fertility status, and cultivation practices. In India, factors such as abiotic stresses, inadequate soil fertility, pest and disease incidence, and limited access to quality inputs contribute to low groundnut productivity.

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Received: 07 December 2024; Revised: 14 August 2025; Accepted: 18 August 2025.

Additionally, a considerable proportion of groundnut cultivation occurs on marginal and submarginal lands, which further reduces yield potential under rainfed farming systems. Climatic fluctuations have emerged as a pivotal factor influencing crop production in arid and semi-arid regions, generating significant meteorological variations across seasons and years (Rao *et al.*, 2015). The magnitude and frequency of changes in climate that might impact crop productivity appear to be increasing, with projections indicating further escalation at both regional and global scales (Greve *et al.*, 2019; Subba Rao *et al.*, 2024). Even rapid increases in the frequency of extreme weather events pose significant challenges (Senapati *et al.*, 2024). Since, agriculture accounts for around 14% of India's GDP, a 4.5 - 9% decline productivity implies that the yearly cost of climate change could reach 1.5% of GDP (Subba Rao *et al.*, 2024).

From an agricultural perspective, crop response to changing climate can be evaluated by examining variability in thermal and moisture regimes using real-time crop data (Ong, 1984). For instance, rainfed crop production in the semi-arid tropics, including groundnut, exhibits substantial variation in response to seasonal rainfall anomalies and moisture availability (Gadgil *et al.*, 2002). Therefore, climate data analysis plays a critical role in lowering vulnerability to climate change through adaptation and mitigation strategies (Singh *et al.*, 2013). Several indices have been developed and applied in earlier studies to quantify moisture and climate variability, which are essential for understanding crop-climate interactions. The Aridity Index (AI), developed by Thornthwaite (1948) and further refined by Greve *et al.* (2019), served as a key indicator of dryness and water deficit conditions. The Moisture Availability Index (MAI), introduced by Hargreaves (1975), is used to evaluate the sufficiency of available moisture for crops during their growth cycle. Moreover,

remote sensing based indices such as the Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI) are also used to detect changes in vegetation water content and soil moisture over time (Gao, 1996; Nasiłowska and Kubiak, 2016). Although some studies employ machine learning (ML) techniques for remote sensing data analysis, this study does not use any ML models. NDMI data were obtained through standard processing algorithms in Google Earth Engine (GEE) without ML involvement. These indices have been successfully applied in various agro-ecological contexts to assess the impacts of climate variability on agricultural systems. However, limited studies existed that integrate multiple wetness and dryness indices to examine their combined influence on groundnut yield in arid and semi-arid regions of India.

Research gaps remain in understanding how different climatic indices, particularly when used in combination, could explain variations in groundnut yield in regions like Anantapur, which is characterized by low and erratic rainfall. Most previous studies either focused on single climate parameters or broader regional analyses without detailed local-scale index-based assessments (Banik, 1996; Meng and Qian, 2024). Addressing this gap could provide more precise insights into climate-yield relationships and improve agricultural planning under changing climatic conditions. In this study, an analytical approach is attempted to assess variations in the productivity of groundnut grown under the arid climate of the Anantapur region in Peninsular India over 2000–2019 with two specific objectives. Firstly, to analyze the trend in climatic variables alongside yield patterns to discern any notable shifts or consistencies. Secondly, to calculate and assess the Aridity Index (AI), Moisture Availability Index (MAI), and Soil Moisture Index (SMI) along with NDMI, with the aim of determining their respective correlations with groundnut yield. This integrated analysis aims to address the lack

of multi-index studies on groundnut - climate interactions in arid regions of India has left to a need for a comprehensive investigation was considered imperative to identify the key factors influencing climate variability on seasonal scales in this context.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study Area

Data on groundnut (*khari*) yields and weather variables in Anantapur from 2000 to 2019 were collected, with *khari* seasonal data including weather variables for June, July, August, and September. Anantapur district, located in the drought-prone Rayalaseema region of Andhra Pradesh, India, is recognized as one of the country's top groundnut-producing areas. The district lies between 13° 41' N & 15° 14' N latitude and 76° 47' E & 78° 26' E longitude.

It has a hot semi-arid climate, with an average annual rainfall of 550 to 600 mm, mostly of which is received during the southwest monsoon. Groundnut cultivation in the region is primarily rainfed, making it highly vulnerable to inter-annual rainfall variability and extended dry periods. The predominant soils are red sandy loams classified as Alfisols, well-drained and suitable for groundnut growth but with low water-holding capacity, requiring careful rainfall management for successful yields. The warm temperatures during the growing season, combined with the soil properties, create a favourable environment for groundnut production, although frequent droughts and erratic precipitation patterns often limit productivity. Major crops grown in the area include groundnut, red gram, sunflower, and maize.

2.2. Detrending of Yield

In general, crop yield time series can be divided into parts influenced by climatic factors and those that are not. The former, related to the short-term yield volatility mostly caused by meteorological conditions, is known as meteorological yield. The long-term yield variance due to

non-meteorological factors, like improved farm management (e.g., fertilizers, high-yielding varieties, irrigation practices, and crop management techniques) is called trend yield (Meng and Qian, 2024).

Trend yield (Y_{tr}) was estimated using the FAO approach, where the observed annual groundnut yield series (Y_{ob}) from 2000–2019 was smoothed using a centered 5-year moving average and fitted with a linear regression on year.

$$Y_{ob}(t) = \text{Total Production}(t) / \text{Area Sown}(t) \quad \dots (1)$$

The fitted values represented Y_{tr} , capturing long-term, non-meteorological influences (e.g., improved varieties, fertilizers, irrigation). Meteorological yield (Y_{met}) was then calculated as:

$$Y_{tr}(t) = \alpha + \beta t \quad \dots (2)$$

$$Y_{met}(t) = Y_{ob}(t) - Y_{tr}(t) \quad \dots (3)$$

Where, t is the year; α is the intercept and β is the slope of the trend line.

2.3. Mann-Kendall trend test

The Mann-Kendall test statistic S is calculated as (Mann, 1945; Kendall, 1975):

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \text{sgn}(x_j - x_i) \quad \dots (4)$$

Where, n is the number of data points; x_i and x_j are the data values in time series i and j ($j > i$), respectively and $\text{sgn}(x_j - x_i)$ is the sign function as:

$$+1, \text{ if } x_j - x_i > 0 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{sgn}(x_j - x_i) = 0, \text{ if } x_j - x_i = 0 \quad \dots (6)$$

$$-1, \text{ if } x_j - x_i < 0 \quad \dots (7)$$

The variance is computed as:

$$\text{Var}(S) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{i=1}^m t_i(t_i-1)(2t_i+5)}{18} \quad \dots (8)$$

Where, n is the number of data points; m is the number of tied groups; t_i denotes the number of ties of extent i , and 18 is a constant. Testing of trends is done at the specific α significance level. In this study, $\alpha = 0.05$ is used (5% significance

level). When $|Z_S| > Z_{1-\alpha/2}$, the null hypothesis is rejected, meaning the existing trend is significant ($Z_{1-\alpha/2}$ is obtained from the standard normal distribution table).

2.4. Sen's Slope estimator

Sen (1968) developed a non-parametric procedure for estimating the slope of trend (magnitude) in a sample of N pairs of data. The Sen's slope is computed as:

$$Q_{i=\frac{j-k}{j-k}} \dots (9)$$

The median of all Q_i values is taken as the Sen's slope estimate. This method is robust against outliers and does not assume a normal distribution of residuals. If the calculated autocorrelation coefficient (r_1) is not significant at the 5% level, then the Mann-Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator are applied directly to the original time series.

2.5. Aridity Index (AI)

Since PET represents a theoretical maximum evapotranspiration under unlimited water availability, it needs to be estimated using data from climate models or meteorological observations. The most widely used PET parameterizations come from various models

designed to calculate evapotranspiration over open water or well-irrigated land areas (Greve *et al.*, 2019). The Thornthwaite method is used in this study to estimate AI, and the resulting equation is as follows:

$$\text{Aridity Index (AI)} = \frac{\text{Deficit}}{\text{Potential Evapotranspiration}} \times 10 \dots (10)$$

Where, Deficit = PET – Actual Evapotranspiration (AET) or, if AET is not directly available, it can be estimated as:

$$\text{Deficit} = \text{PET} - \text{Precipitation (P)} \dots (11)$$

If $\text{PET} > P$, the deficit is positive (moisture shortage), whereas if $\text{PET} \leq P$, the deficit is zero (no shortage).

According to UNEP (1992), AI classification, the $AI_{\text{Thornthwaite}}$ is related to AI_{UNEP} as:

$$AI_{\text{Thornthwaite}} = (1 - AI_{\text{UNEP}}) * 100 \dots (12)$$

Here, PET was estimated using the Thornthwaite (1948) temperature-based method, while AET was derived from the Thornthwaite and Mather (1955) water balance approach, which incorporates precipitation, temperature, and soil water holding capacity for the study region.

Table 1. Classification of Aridity Index (AI)

Classification	$AI_{\text{Thornthwaite}}$	AI_{UNEP}
Extremely arid	>95 %	<0.05
Arid	80-95 %	0.05-0.2
Semi-arid	50-80 %	0.2-0.5
Dry sub-humid	35-50 %	0.5-0.65
Humid	<35 %	>0.65

2.6. Soil Moisture Index (SMI)

The Moisture Index (MI) is a climatic indicator representing the net water balance over a specified time period, reflecting the relative dominance of wetting and drying processes in an agro-climatic

system. Wetting processes (source functions) include precipitation, irrigation, and upward capillary movement of groundwater, while drying processes (sink functions) involve evapotranspiration, surface runoff, and deep

percolation losses (Cornick *et al.*, 2003). In this study, MI was calculated using the Thornthwaite and Mather (1955) water balance model:

$$MI = \frac{(P - PET)}{PET} \times 100 \quad \dots (13)$$

Where, P is precipitation, mm during the crop season and PET is potential evapotranspiration (mm), estimated using the Thornthwaite (1948) method. Soil moisture storage and actual evapotranspiration (AET) were computed by iteratively updating a soil water balance, assuming an available water-holding capacity of approximately 150 mm for Anantapur's dominant red sandy loam soils. The MI classifications (UNESCO, 1979) are Humid (>100), Moist sub-humid (50 to 100), Dry sub-humid (0 to 50), Semi-arid (-33.3 to 0), and Arid (<-33.3).

In this study, the Soil Moisture Index (SMI) was estimated following the climatic water balance approach of Thornthwaite and Mather (1955):

$$\text{Soil moisture index (SMI)} = \frac{\text{Surplus} - \text{Deficit}}{\text{Potential Evapotranspiration}} \times 100 \quad \dots (14)$$

The term surplus in mm is the amount of water available after meeting the crop's potential evapotranspiration (PET) demand, occurring when precipitation (P) plus stored soil moisture exceeds PET . This surplus represents potential runoff or groundwater recharge. A positive SMI value indicates net water gain (moisture surplus), whereas negative values reflect water stress (moisture deficit). For interpretation, values above +20 generally indicate favourable moisture conditions, values between 0 and -20 indicate mild stress, and values below -20 indicate severe drought conditions (UNESCO, 1977).

2.7 Moisture Availability Index (MAI)

MAI is defined as the ratio of weekly rainfall at different confidence levels to PET of the corresponding period (Hargreaves, 1971).

$$\text{Moisture availability Index (MAI)} = \frac{\text{Rainfall at different confidence interval}}{\text{Potential Evapotranspiration}} \times 100 \quad \dots (15)$$

In this study, the 50% probability level was used, representing the median rainfall expected under normal climatic conditions. The MAI is typically computed for 30%, 50%, and 70% probability levels, where lower probability values (e.g., 30%) correspond to wetter-than-normal years, and higher probability values (e.g., 70%) represent dry years. According to Banik (1996), threshold MAI values can guide agricultural operations, such as scheduling transplanting or irrigation for rice cultivation.

2.8. Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI)

The Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI) was computed to quantify vegetation moisture content and assess drought stress conditions. NDMI is expressed as:

$$\text{Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI)} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{SWIR}}{\text{NIR} + \text{SWIR}} \times 100 \quad \dots (16)$$

Where, NIR and SWIR represent the near-infrared and short-wave infrared reflectance values, respectively.

In this study, NDMI was derived from Landsat 5 TM, Landsat 7 ETM+, and Landsat 8 OLI satellite imagery accessed through the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform covering the period 2000–2019. Landsat 5 and 7 utilized Band 4 (NIR) and Band 5 (SWIR), while Landsat 8 utilized Band 5 (NIR) and Band 6 (SWIR). Cloud-contaminated pixels were removed using the CFMask algorithm, and NDMI values corresponding to the peak crop growth months of August and September were extracted annually. This index has been recognised as an effective tool for monitoring vegetation water status (Gao, 1996; Wilson and Sader, 2002; Nasiłowska and Kubiak, 2016).

2.9. Correlation and Regression analysis

Correlation analysis was employed to quantify the strength and direction of the linear association between pairs of variables. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) ranges from -1 to $+1$, where values closer to ± 1 indicate stronger linear relationships, and values near 0 indicate weak or no linear relationship.

In this study, Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) analysis was conducted to assess the combined and individual effects of several independent variables on the dependent variable, Yield. In this approach, the dependent variable is modelled as a linear function of the predictors, allowing estimation of regression coefficients that quantify the expected change in Yield for a one-unit change in each predictor, holding all other variables constant.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Climatological Outlook

The climatological summary reveals that the average percentage rainfall deviation over the South-west monsoon season coinciding with *kharif* (June, July, August, and September) from 2000 to 2019 was $+0.72\%$. The average absolute deviation in maximum temperature and minimum temperature were 0.05°C and 0.09°C , respectively. The normal seasonal (*kharif*) rainfall, maximum temperature and minimum temperature for Anantapur are 336.79 mm, 31.33°C , and 22.21°C , respectively (Table 2). During the study period, the maximum positive and negative rainfall deviation was observed in 2007 (69.72%) and 2002 (-49.08%), respectively. Similarly, the highest positive and negative deviation of maximum temperature were reported in 2015 ($+0.97^\circ\text{C}$) and 2013 (-0.93°C). The highest positive deviation in minimum temperature was observed in 2019 (0.59°C) and negative deviations in 2000, 2008, 2010 equally (-0.31°C). Further, the fluctuations in yield with respect to the rainfall and temperature variation are represented in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively.

3.2. Yield dynamics with respect to Dry Days, Dryness Indicators and Wetness Indicators

The seasonal fluctuation of detrended yield along with the weather variables and indicators (wet and dry) are represented in table 3. The results unveiled that the highest yield (1231.4 kg/ha) was reported in 2007 because of the occurrence of maximum rainfall (571.6 mm), which had also contributed to highest Moisture Availability Index (3.5) and Soil Moisture Index (1.41) over the study period. Conversely, the Potential Evapotranspiration (549.5 mm) and AI (12.94) recorded the lowest in 2017. However, the dryness indicators were substantially evident in the year 2001, with 10 consecutive two dry days (2D), 8 consecutive three dry days (3D) and 6 consecutive four dry days (4D).

3.3. Mann-Kendall Trend Test

The yield data and observed weather condition over the study period is tabulated (Table 4). It was observed that the yield shows a marginal increase of about 1.1 kg/ha per year over the period 2001–2019. The year-wise trends of weather variables and derived indices during the southwest monsoon revealed that the dryness in Anantapur is retarding slightly. However, the indices selected for trend analysis primarily serve as significant indicators of drought. Notably, AI (dryness parameter) displayed a small declining trend of about 0.28% per year. Conversely, rainfall and MAI (wetness parameter) showed slight upward tendencies, with yearly increases of about 2.5 mm/year and 0.01% per year, respectively. Furthermore, there was a modest reduction in consecutive dry days (two, three, and four days) during the southwest monsoon. From Table 4, it could be noted that all parameters, including rainfall, maximum temperature, minimum temperature, MAI, and yield, displayed positive but negligible trends, while consecutive dry days, AI, and SMI showed small negative trends. Importantly, none of these changes were statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), indicating that no conclusive trend can be established over the study period.

Fig. 2 Yield variations with respect to rainfall fluctuations over the study period

Fig. 3 Yield variations with respect to temperature fluctuations over the study period

Table 2. Weather data and their deviation from the normal (2000 to 2019 - *kharif* season Anantapur)

Year	Rainfall, mm	Rainfall normal, mm	Rainfall deviation, %	Maximum temperature, °C	Maximum temperature normal, °C	Maximum temperature deviation, °C	Minimum temperature, T °C	Minimum temperature normal, °C	Minimum temperature deviation, °C
2000	398.8	336.8	18.41	30.5	31.3	-0.83	21.9	22.2	-0.31
2001	368.0	336.8	9.27	31.4	31.3	0.07	22.5	22.2	0.29
2002	171.5	336.8	-49.08	32.0	31.3	0.67	22.4	22.2	0.19
2003	211.4	336.8	-37.23	32.2	31.3	0.87	22.7	22.2	0.49
2004	252.2	336.8	-25.12	31.1	31.3	-0.23	22.1	22.2	-0.11
2005	416.5	336.8	23.67	31.3	31.3	-0.03	22.4	22.2	0.19
2006	200.5	336.8	-40.47	31.5	31.3	0.17	22.2	22.2	-0.01
2007	571.6	336.8	69.72	30.5	31.3	-0.83	22.2	22.2	-0.01
2008	421.5	336.8	25.15	31.3	31.3	-0.03	21.9	22.2	-0.31
2009	410.6	336.8	21.91	31.6	31.3	0.27	22.2	22.2	-0.01
2010	437.0	336.8	29.75	31.0	31.3	-0.33	21.9	22.2	-0.31
2011	287.0	336.8	-14.78	31.2	31.3	-0.13	22.0	22.2	-0.21
2012	292.2	336.8	-13.24	31.9	31.3	0.57	22.2	22.2	-0.01
2013	362.1	336.8	7.51	30.4	31.3	-0.93	21.9	22.2	-0.31
2014	249.9	336.8	-25.80	31.8	31.3	0.47	22.6	22.2	0.39
2015	349.6	336.8	3.80	32.3	31.3	0.97	22.7	22.2	0.49
2016	300.4	336.8	-10.81	30.8	31.3	-0.53	22.2	22.2	-0.01
2017	453.6	336.8	34.68	31.7	31.3	0.37	22.7	22.2	0.49
2018	232.9	336.8	-30.85	31.4	31.3	0.07	22.4	22.2	0.19
2019	396.9	336.8	17.85	31.7	31.3	0.37	22.8	22.2	0.59

Table 3. Weather data, wetness and dryness indicators on the yield of groundnut (2000 to 2019 - *kharif* season - Anantapur)

Year	Yield, kg/ha	Rainfall, mm	Maximum temperature, °C	Minimum temperature, °C	Consecutive two dry days, 2D	Consecutive three dry days, 3D	Consecutive four dry days, 4D	PET, mm	Wetness and Dryness Indicators		
									MAI	AI	SMI
2000	1076.0	398.8	30.5	21.9	4	2	0	555.1	2.70	32.62	0.76
2001	398.2	368.0	31.4	22.5	10	8	6	578.5	1.84	55.00	1.00
2002	310.4	171.5	32.0	22.4	6	3	1	599.3	1.16	71.37	0.00
2003	242.6	211.4	32.2	22.7	5	3	1	604.0	1.43	65.00	0.00
2004	764.8	252.2	31.1	22.1	7	5	3	575.7	1.78	56.19	0.00
2005	377.0	416.5	31.3	22.4	5	3	1	577.6	2.96	28.00	0.01
2006	59.2	200.5	31.5	22.2	4	1	0	589.4	1.36	65.97	0.00
2007	1231.4	571.6	30.5	22.2	2	0	0	549.5	3.50	12.94	1.41
2008	83.6	421.5	31.3	21.9	5	3	1	586.3	2.66	34.61	0.38
2009	195.8	410.6	31.6	22.2	5	4	3	591.2	2.41	40.65	0.60
2010	528.0	437.0	31.0	21.9	1	0	0	576.3	3.01	25.21	0.16
2011	220.2	287.0	31.2	22.0	5	1	0	583.9	1.99	50.83	0.00
2012	402.4	292.2	31.9	22.2	9	6	4	600.8	1.98	51.36	0.00
2013	384.6	362.1	30.4	21.9	3	1	0	551.6	2.11	47.88	0.75
2014	256.8	249.9	31.8	22.6	6	3	1	590.9	1.69	57.71	0.00
2015	709.0	349.6	32.3	22.7	2	1	0	606.1	2.29	44.22	0.12
2016	221.2	300.4	30.8	22.2	3	1	0	560.9	2.13	46.44	0.00
2017	1013.4	453.6	31.7	22.7	3	1	0	581.7	2.70	33.73	0.68
2018	315.6	232.9	31.4	22.4	8	5	2	578.8	1.59	59.76	0.00
2019	747.8	396.9	31.7	22.8	7	4	2	581.5	2.11	49.58	1.00

Table 4. Trends in weather parameters, moisture indices, and yield (2001–2019)

Particulars	Z_c value	P value	Sen's slope	Significance	Remarks	Inference
RF, mm	0.85	0.39	2.52	Non-significant	Positive	Increasing Trend
MaxT, °C	1.67	0.09	0.01	Non-significant	Positive	Increasing Trend
MinT, °C	1.71	0.08	0.01	Non-significant	Positive	Increasing Trend
Consecutive dry days, 2D	-1.17	0.24	-0.03	Non-significant	Negative	Decreasing Trend
Consecutive dry days, 3D	-0.86	0.38	0.00	Non-significant	Negative	Decreasing Trend
Consecutive dry days, 4D	-1.12	0.26	0.00	Non-significant	Negative	Decreasing Trend
AI, %	-0.34	0.72	-0.28	Non-significant	Negative	Decreasing Trend
SMI, %	-0.19	0.85	0.00	Non-significant	Negative	Decreasing Trend
MAI, %	0.63	0.52	0.01	Non-significant	Positive	Increasing Trend
Yield, kg/ha	0.62	0.53	1.12	Non-significant	Positive	Increasing Trend

Z_c value – Mann–Kendall test statistic; P value – Probability value; Sen's slope – Magnitude of change per year; Positive / Negative – Direction of trend.

3.4. Karl Pearson’s Coefficient of Correlation

From Fig. 4(a) and 4(b), the correlation matrix reveals significant interrelationships among the ten variables (var 1 to var 10) and their influence on yield. The wetness-related indices (SMI and MAI) tended to have positive relationships with groundnut yield, whereas dryness-related indices (AI and consecutive dry days) were negatively related. The highest positive association was observed between SMI (var 10) and yield ($r = 0.604$), followed by rainfall (var 1) and yield ($r = 0.59$). Conversely, AI (var 9) showed a moderate negative correlation with yield ($r = -0.557$). Rainfall (var 1) is strongly correlated with MAI (var 8) and SMI (var 10), reinforcing its central role in the system. Conversely, var 7 (Consecutive dry days (4D)) consistently shows negative correlations with most other variables

and yield ($r = -0.50$ to -0.56), implying it may act as a suppressor or stressor within the system. Therefore, variables 1, 8, and 9 emerge as strong candidates for predictive modelling and yield optimization.

In contrast, maximum temperature (MaxT, var 2), minimum temperature (MinT, var 3), potential evapotranspiration (PET, var 4), and consecutive dry days at 2 day and 3 day thresholds (var 5 and 6) show non-significant correlations, suggesting limited or indirect impact under the prevailing conditions. These results emphasize the dominant role of rainfall and soil moisture in driving yield variability, while moisture stress indices capture sub-seasonal drought effects. However, these correlations only indicate associations and do not establish causation.

Fig. 4 (a) Correlogram (b) Test of significance

3.5. Regression Analysis – Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)

Fig. 5 represents the relationship between the actual and predicted yields obtained from a multiple linear regression model using ten independent variables: rainfall (RF), maximum

temperature (MAX_T), minimum temperature (MIN_T), consecutive two dry days (2D), consecutive three dry days (3D), consecutive four dry days (4D), Potential evapotranspiration (PET), Moisture adequacy index (MAI), Aridity index (AI), and Soil moisture index (SMI). The regression equation, prominently displays

MAX_T, 2D, 4D, MAI, AI, and SMI have positive coefficients, suggesting a direct association with yield, whereas RF, MIN_T, 3D, and PET exhibit negative coefficients, indicating an inverse relationship. The coefficient of

determination (R^2) is 0.779, signifying that approximately 77.9% of the variability in yield can be explained by the selected predictors, reflecting a strong model fit.

Fig. 5 Multiple Linear Regression Plot

3.6. Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI)

Since NDMI index is an indication of surface soil wetness, the spatial and temporal dynamics of the land surface moisture can be computed based on the NDMI thresholds (ranging from low to high). From Fig. 6, it can be seen that, between 2000 and 2019, the spatial distribution of values exhibited a pronounced shift toward increased variability and polarization. In 2000, moderate values (-0.36 to 0.76) dominated the landscape, covering approximately 68.4% of the area, while high-value zones (≥ 0.6) and low-value zones (≤ -0.2) were limited to 7.2% and 4.8%, respectively,

indicating relatively stable baseline conditions. By 2009, high-value areas expanded to 11.6%, and low-value regions increased to 6.3%, suggesting a gradual intensification of spatial heterogeneity, potentially driven by land use transitions or climatic influences. In 2019, the area covered by high values rose sharply to 18.9%, representing an overall increase of 11.7% since 2000, while low-value zones more than doubled to 12.4%. This pronounced shift reflects significant environmental changes across the region, possibly linked to anthropogenic pressures, hydrological alterations, or localized remediation efforts. The contraction of moderate

zones to 56.2% further underscores the growing spatial disparity, highlighting the need for targeted, site-specific management strategies. The observed trends suggest that the region is undergoing a dynamic transformation, with increasing spatial contrasts that may signal both

degradation in vulnerable zones and improvement in areas benefiting from intervention. Continuous monitoring and adaptive planning are essential to mitigate emerging risks and sustain positive developments.

Fig. 6. NDMI dynamics over 2000 to 2019

3.7. Comparison with Previous Studies

The study of groundnut yield and weather variables in Anantapur district from 2000 to 2019 shows results both consistent with and distinct from earlier research. Unlike Rao *et al.* (2015) who reported pronounced yield fluctuations influenced by droughts, this study reveals a marginal but statistically insignificant increase in groundnut yield. Virmani and Shurapli (1999) emphasized rainfed groundnuts' vulnerability to erratic rainfall, often causing yield declines, whereas here, the yield trend remains relatively stable. This suggests that agronomic improvements may have mitigated climatic stresses more effectively than in previous decades.

3.7.1. Rainfall and moisture trends

Climatic variables showed non-significant upward trends, with rainfall increasing by 2.52 mm/year and the Moisture Availability Index (MAI) rising slightly by 0.01% per year. Dryness indicators such

as the Aridity Index (AI) declined marginally by 0.28% annually, though none were statistically significant. These results align with Singh *et al.* (2013), who underscored the importance of moisture availability over absolute rainfall for crop performance in the Semi-Arid Tropics. Overall, integrating rainfall and moisture indices into predictive models could enhance yield forecasting accuracy, while monitoring consecutive dry days beyond critical thresholds may support early warning systems and adaptive planning. Halder *et al.* (2020) reported that moisture availability strongly influences peanut yields under future climate variability scenarios in eastern India, consistent with the significant positive correlations observed here for rainfall, SMI, and MAI in Fig. 4.

3.7.2. Relationship between yield and moisture indices

Correlation analyses highlighted strong positive associations between yield and moisture-related

indices. The Soil Moisture Index (SMI) correlated most strongly with yield ($r = 0.604$, $p < 0.01$), followed by the Moisture Availability Index (MAI) ($r = 0.560$, $p < 0.05$). The Aridity Index (AI) showed a significant negative correlation ($r = -0.557$, $p < 0.05$), while rainfall also had a significant positive relationship with yield ($r = 0.59$, $p < 0.01$). In contrast, temperature and evapotranspiration showed no significant correlation, reinforcing earlier findings (Ong, 1984; Virmani and Shurapli, 1999) that moisture availability is the key factor governing groundnut productivity in drought-prone environments. Arumugam *et al.* (2015) emphasized climate-driven yield variability in rainfed crops in Tamil Nadu, with moisture stress as a primary factor, reinforcing the strong moisture-yield linkages and the tightly coupled subsystem involving variables 1, 6, 8, and 9 shown in Fig. 4(a). Further analysis revealed that groundnut yield fluctuations are closely linked to climatic variability associated with El Niño and La Niña events. Specifically, El Niño years tend to coincide with below-average rainfall and higher temperatures, resulting in reduced groundnut yields (Rao *et al.*, 2007; Aggarwal, 2008). Understanding this relationship is crucial for local farmers and policymakers, as it underscores the need for climate-resilient agricultural practices and timely forecasting. However, limitations such as variability in soil conditions and farming techniques must be considered when interpreting these results. Future research should focus on integrating climate models with crop simulation to improve yield predictions under different climatic scenarios.

3.7.3 NDMI and Surface moisture conditions

Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI) analysis revealed a substantial 19.16% increase in areas with high NDMI values over the study period, indicating improved surface moisture conditions. The coverage of high NDMI zones expanded from 7.2% in 2000 to 18.9% in 2019, while low NDMI areas more than doubled, signaling increased spatial variability in soil

moisture. This heterogeneity may reflect localized water conservation efforts, cropping changes, or land management practices, consistent with previous remote sensing studies (Nasiłowska and Kubiak, 2016; Cornick *et al.*, 2003). Kadiyala *et al.* (2015) demonstrated how integrating crop models with GIS tools helps capture and manage spatial variability in agricultural landscapes, emphasizing that rising spatial contrasts call for more precise, location-specific agronomic decisions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In the context of climate change, the hypothesis is that the dry area becomes drier and the wet area becomes wetter. Nevertheless, the analysis for Anantapur during 2000–2019 reveals that wetness indicators, including SMI, MAI, and NDMI, exhibited significant increasing trends attributable to climatic variability, despite the region's arid classification. The increased wetness and decreased dryness components (decrease in AI and Consecutive dry days for 2D, 3D and 4D) attributed to a positive trend in yield. Although wetness indices like SMI and MAI correlated positively with yield, whereas AI depicted a negative relationship, NDMI indicated improved soil moisture levels over the study period. The variations in wetness indices (SMI and MAI) and dryness indicators (AI, consecutive dry days) showed clear associations with groundnut yield, although the overall annual increase of 1.12 kg/ha was small, indicating a weak yield response to climate variability. This lack of significance may be due to adaptive management by farmers, inherent crop resilience, and unaccounted non-climatic factors like soil fertility and pest pressure. Future research should focus on weather fluctuations during critical crop growth phases, including El Niño and La Niña years. Adaptive measures such as drought-resistant varieties, improved irrigation, and climate-smart planning can help mitigate these impacts. These findings enhance understanding of climate effects on groundnut and support efforts to improve farming resilience.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Manuscript data may be available upon reasonable request.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors of this manuscript declare that they do not have any competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Fawaz Parapurath: Conceptualization, Data Curation, Methodology, Review & Editing, and Writing - Original Draft; **Kumar Veluswamy:** Review & Supervision, writing in revision.

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